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For background information on the Training Certification, please see the [FAQs](#).

Full author information is available in [Appendix A](#).

Preamble

- A. Please provide the submitter details.
 - a. Name:
 - b. Email:
 - c. Affiliation:
- B. Is this a resubmission? If so, please provide the link to the previous application.
- C. What is the name of the resource:
- D. What is the type of the resource:
 - a. course, or
 - b. training material

Evaluation questions

1. Does the resource have all the minimal descriptors of the BioSchemas profile¹?
 - a. Yes, or
 - b. No
2. Are the following FAIR Training recommendations addressed by the training material? (a checklist based on a subset of the *Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR*²)
 - Rule 1: Your training materials are shared online
Please provide a link to the training materials:
 - Rule 2: Improve findability of your training materials by properly describing them
Is there a short overview of the training materials: Yes/No
 - Rule 3: Give your training materials a unique identity
Please share the identifier in URL format:
 - Rule 4: Register your training materials online
Are the training materials registered in TeSS: Yes/No
 - Rule 5: Define access rules for your training materials
Are access rules stated: Yes/No
 - Rule 6: Use an interoperable format for your training materials
Please list the interoperable formats that have been used:
 - Rule 7: Make your training materials (re)usable for trainers
Please describe shortly how reusability is achieved:

¹ <https://bioschemas.org/groups/Training>

² Garcia, Leyla, et al. "[Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR](#)." *PLOS Computational Biology* 16.5 (2020): e1007854.

3. Is the level that the learners' knowledge will reach on the topic specified?
For a definition of the novice, intermediate and advanced levels, please refer to these relevant resources: Bioinformatic Mastery Rubric³, with a corresponding introduction⁴ and a professional guide⁵, and the ELIXIR Train-the-Trainer course⁶.
 - a. Yes, with one or more of the below options:
 - Novice
 - Intermediate
 - Advanced, or
 - b. No

4. Is the target audience explicitly written/defined?
 - a. Yes
Please share the definition used:
 - b. No

5. Are prerequisites described?
These include both technical, such as required software/hardware and respective skills, and training-related, such as prior experience and knowledge. Ideally, all knowledge- and skill-related prerequisites should be defined using actionable verbs (i.e. Bloom's).
 - a. Yes
Please share any supporting text, e.g., across technical and training-related:
 - b. No

6. Are the learning outcomes explicitly written/defined, e.g., is there such a section included in the description?
 - a. Yes
Please share any supporting text, e.g., list of learning outcomes:
 - b. No

7. Are learning outcomes written using actionable verbs (i.e. Bloom's)?
 - a. Yes
Please share any supporting text, e.g., list of verbs used:
 - b. No

8. Is the Training Event registered in TeSS?
Ideally, most of the information listed in this certification document should also be listed under TeSS in the respective fields.
 - a. Yes
Please share the URL:
 - b. No

³ Tractenberg, Rochelle E., et al. "[The Mastery Rubric for Bioinformatics: A tool to support design and evaluation of career-spanning education and training](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222525)" *PLoS One* 14.11 (2019): e02225256.

⁴ <https://f1000research.com/documents/11-735>

⁵ <https://f1000research.com/documents/11-743>

⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training/train-the-trainer>

⁷ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

9. Will the Training Event adopt the ELIXIR feedback questionnaires (both short-term and long-term)⁸?
Note: Please do not share any link to the survey results.
- Yes
Please share supporting text, e.g., URL of the survey and/or template of the survey that will be used, and the statement about it in the course description.
 - No
10. Is the training event organised by one or more ELIXIR Nodes?
- Yes
Please share the list of ELIXIR Nodes:
 - No
11. Will the course include at least one instructor who has attended a formal pedagogical course (such as the ELIXIR TtT course)?
- Yes
Please specify which instructors attended which course:
 - No
12. Does the course abide by the ELIXIR Code of Conduct⁹?
- Yes
Please share supporting text from the description:
 - No
 - Not applicable
This submission is only for training materials, not a training event.
 - Other
Please share supporting text, and the link to the Code of Conduct used:
13. Are participants informed of any collected usage data (e.g. names or emails of participants, images, videos if recorded, or pictures were taken)?
Note: data collection should be compliant with the GDPR rules, based on the local regulations of the organising Institution
- Yes
Please share supporting text from the description:
 - No

⁸ <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database/wiki>

⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/code-of-conduct>

Self Assessment questions

Note: these are not part of the certification assessment.

- Are the learning outcomes SMART?
- Is the course content aligned with the learning outcomes?
- Are the included exercises (e.g., formative assessment, evaluation, etc) aligned with the learning outcomes?
- Does the course actively attempt to ensure diversity, inclusion, equal opportunities and balance for both participants and instructors? (e.g., include specific statements to this effect, such as the criteria for participant selection, in the course description?)
- How do you intend to follow the last three of the *Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR*?
 - *Rule 8: Make your training materials usable for trainees*
 - *Rule 9: Make your training materials contribution friendly*
 - *Rule 10: Plan to keep your training materials up-to-date*

FAQs

What is Training Certification?

Training Certification refers to a formal recognition or endorsement awarded to a training course or program upon meeting specific criteria and standards as envisioned and endorsed by the ELIXIR Training Platform¹⁰. The purpose is to verify that the course or material meets certain quality, content, and educational standards, ensuring learners gain valuable knowledge and skills.

What are the implications of Training Certification?

- Quality Assurance - Indicates the course has undergone rigorous evaluation to meet standards.
- Credibility - Certified courses carry more credibility and are often preferred for enhancing knowledge/skills.
- Competency - Implies learners will possess competency in the subject matter upon completion.
- Alignment with standards - Often indicates the course adheres to industry or professional standards.
- Continuous improvement - Maintaining certification may require periodic reviews and updates.

What is within the remit of Training Certification and what is beyond?

Certification of participants is beyond the current scope but may be addressed in the future.

What are the benefits of Certification for ELIXIR?

1. Offer a standard for all training events under the ELIXIR badge.
2. Have a large portfolio of certified events from all Nodes.
3. Provide evidence of performance/impact in digital skills/training to funders.
4. Offer a portfolio that guarantees quality to end-users seeking training.
5. Training can belong to ELIXIR Services/Communities/Platforms.
6. Increased visibility and awareness of ELIXIR's existence.
7. Clear indication of which events can display the ELIXIR Training logo.
8. A new tool for ELIXIR and the Nodes, like CDR and RIR.

What are the benefits for the Nodes?

1. Quality assurance of contents and training practices.
2. Possibility to obtain ELIXIR funding.
3. Increased exposure/visibility of national resources and training.
4. Better exposure and discoverability via ELIXIR.
5. Support to build training capacity and professional development.
6. Becoming part of the ELIXIR Training community.
7. Opportunities to participate in training-related proposals.

¹⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training>

What are the benefits for trainees?

1. Reassurance the training has value aligned with best practices.
2. Certification will gain importance for trainees over time.
3. Potential for increased employability.

What are the benefits for trainers?

Evidence of being part of a pan-European effort. Better employability and references.

What are potential concerns with Training Certification?

- Training offered by other projects/networks/institutions.
- Linking certification directly to funding.
- Allowing non-certified ELIXIR training.
- Inconsistencies in communicating certification to trainees.
- Aligning with diverse training communities like Galaxy.

What is the proposed certification process?

Preliminary discussions have yielded a process

- Certification Committee
 - 2 (+ committee for resolution, if there are significant conflicts in the review)
 - Ideally reviewers familiar with ELIXIR Training Platform, Train-the-Trainer and FAIR
 - Onboarding process (pairing reviewers)
- Open, public evaluation
 - Reviewer to confirm the Yes/No based on the supporting text
 - Names of committee and reviewers to be open
 - The application (and the reviews) should be up to the applicant to decide whether it should be open or not.
- Certificate duration is time-limited (not infinite)
 - If a course/material has already been certified, the recertification process will be simplified (e.g. submit same form but adding a cover letter with any changes that have happened since previous iteration)
 - Associate the date, duration and particular course instance¹¹/material of the certification to the "badge"
- Application Process
 - Open all the time (anyone can submit at any time)
- Certification steps
 1. Application goes to the committee.
 2. Committee does a first assessment and sends to the Slack / pool of reviewers asking for reviewers 1st-come-1st-serve (1 week)
 3. Two Reviewers evaluate and provide feedback (2 weeks)
 - Two independent concurrent evaluations of the application, with each reviewer provides two items per question:

¹¹ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/CourseInstance/1.0-RELEASE>

Training Certification Criteria v1.1.1

- A mandatory Yes/No (on whether the application statement is supported by the text)
 - An optional free-text comment, for any additional thoughts that need to be shared/communicated to the applicant
 - The expectation is that both reviews will be exactly the same (Yes/No in the questions)
 - If there are any conflicts, a consensus needs to be reached between the two reviewers. If impossible, this goes to the Committee that will then need to make the final decision.
4. Committee responds back to the applicant (3 days) with a Yes/No response based on threshold:
- Threshold: 11-14 -> YES / 0-10 -> NO (aka 3 "No"s)
 - Learn on how this works in practice, and update the process in the 2nd year
5. After a "No" decision, an applicant can resubmit the same application for a revision following a scaled process:
- First resubmission: 2 weeks
 - 2nd resubmission: 1 month
 - 3rd resubmission: 2 months

Appendix A - Author list

Authors are listed alphabetically by last name.

We thank equally the many other contributors of the Certification working group, including those part of [Task 2 Gap analysis, training materials development and training delivery](#) of the 2022-2023 work programme of the ELIXIR Training Platform.

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Appendix B - Evaluation questions v1.0.1

	Question	Potential responses
1	Does the resource have the minimal descriptors of the BioSchemas profile? (will require a subset of the BioSchemas list)	Yes/No + supported by a checklist of multiple items
2	Are the following FAIR Training “principles”/aspects addressed by the training material? (a checklist based on a subset of the 10SR FAIR Training)	Yes/No + supported by checklist of multiple items (incl. DOI)
3	Is the level that the learners’ knowledge will reach on the topic specified? (For a definition of the novice, intermediate and advanced levels, please refer to these relevant resources: Bioinformatic Mastery Rubric + Professional Guide + ELIXIR TtT course + ???) doi: 10.7490/f1000research.1119019.1 doi: 10.7490/f1000research.1119023.1	Yes/No + One or more of the below options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Novice ● Intermediate ● Advanced
4	Is the target audience explicitly written/defined?	Yes/No + supporting text (e.g. c&p of the definition used)
5	Are prerequisites described? These include both technical (such as required software/hardware and respective skills) and training-related (such as prior experience and knowledge) Ideally, all knowledge- and skill-related prerequisites should be defined using actionable verbs (i.e. Bloom’s).	Yes/No + supporting text (e.g. across technical and training-related)
6	Are the learning outcomes explicitly written/defined (e.g. is a section “Learning Outcomes” included in the description)?	Yes/No + supporting text (e.g. list of LO)
7	Are learning outcomes written using actionable verbs (i.e. Bloom’s)?	Yes/No + supporting text (e.g. list of verbs used)
8	Is the Training Event registered in TeSS? If so, please list the URL Ideally, all information listed in this certification document, should also be listed under TeSS in the respective fields.	Yes/No + URL
9	Is the Training Material registered in TeSS? If so, please list the URL. Ideally, all information listed in this certification document, should also be listed under TeSS in the respective fields.	Yes/No + URL
10	Will the Training Event adopt the ELIXIR feedback questionnaires (both short-term and long-term)?	Yes/No + supporting text (URL of the survey and/or template of the survey that

	(Please, do not share any link to the survey results.)	will be used + the statement about it in the course description)
11	<p>Is the training event organised by one or more ELIXIR Nodes?</p> <p>(This is the first round of certification, so it's primarily targeted towards resources that are directly supported by ELIXIR. This will be updated/amended accordingly for future iterations.)</p>	<p>Checklist of all Nodes. - Yes (if yes a list of nodes, and the possibility to choose more than one)</p> <p>- No (if no, go to next question)</p>
12	<p>Will the course include at least one instructor who has attended a formal pedagogical course (such as the ELIXIR TtT course)?</p>	<p>Yes/No + Instructor(s) name(s) (+ supporting statement on the TtT course attended)</p>
13	<p>Does the course abide by the ELIXIR Code of Conduct?</p>	<p>Yes/No + supporting text (c&p statement from the description)</p>
14	<p>Are participants informed of any collected usage data (e.g. names or emails of participants, images, videos if recorded, or pictures were taken)?</p> <p>(data collection should be compliant to the GDPR rules, based on the local regulations in of the organising Institution)</p>	<p>Yes/No + supporting text (c&p statement from the description)</p>